

Research Article

Language, Experience, and Autism: Understanding Popular Sayings and the Limits of Symbolic Empathy. Neurolinguistics. Therapeutically Relevant Neurolinguistic Processes

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Abstract

People with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) frequently struggle to understand proverbs and metaphoric expressions. This article argues that such difficulties are not due to a mere cognitive limitation but stem from an absence of shared, emotionally-rooted experiences that give rise to symbolic language. Based on neuropsychological concepts such as mirror neurons, secondary self, and experiential context, we propose that the autistic individual often learns language through lexical imposition, detached from interpersonal interaction. We also discuss therapeutic implications, criticizing the indiscriminate use of behavioral approaches, such as ABA, in favor of relational models like the French “Therapies exchanges et de Développement”. This work aims to broaden clinical understanding and point to more humanized, experience-based interventions.

Keywords: autism; metaphor; proverbs; mirror neuron; language acquisition; symbolic self; developmental therapy

Introduction

This article arose from a practical question: why do people with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) have so much difficulty understanding popular sayings? Expressions like “the neighbor’s chicken is fatter” are taken literally, without access to the symbolic meaning – in this case, envy, a universal trait of human experience. To understand this, it is necessary to delve into the mechanisms of language acquisition and the construction of the symbolic self in autism.

Expressions like “the neighbor’s chicken is fatter” are commonly interpreted literally by people with autism, revealing the difficulty in understanding symbols, metaphors, and shared contexts. This limitation goes beyond the lexical field and points to deficits in symbolic constitution, empathy, and internal narrative construction. The objective of this article is to discuss the neuropsychological and clinical bases of this phenomenon, relating them to therapeutic practice and the critique of mechanized methods.

What motivated us to write this article was a question: why do people with autism spectrum disorder have difficulties in solving popular sayings, in understanding the context, in understanding the meaning of popular sayings? For example, if you say “the neighbor’s chicken is always fatter,” some will understand that you are saying the neighbor’s chicken is fatter – and not talking about envy, which is a natural human feeling. Let’s try to explain. First of all, of course, there are various degrees of autism, but let’s take a typical case.

He imposes the lexicon. He tends to understand words as little signs that are placed for him. Inclusive, there are methods like Loovas-ABA that do this. In our view, in some circumstances, they reinforce the pathology, because they tend to understand language as an imposition – and not as a context where the word is used, for example, “open the door and come here”. Normally, the child does not learn to say “door” out of nowhere. The person says: “come to daddy, close the door and come to daddy”. So, the person learns to speak in a living context. And then the father talks to the child, and the child who has a good mirror neuron system assimilates that situation of “coming to daddy and closing the door” to learn the word “door”. The father does not usually come to the child and say “door, door, door,” and impose that on their mind.

On the other hand, the child with autism (of course, depending on the degree and variants) does not elaborate the phrase, because that phrase you have to live it – and see yourself living it, see yourself experiencing that phrase. For example, when you are going to talk about “door,” you will have to remember, or feel, or re-experience that you lived that word with your father, and that at that moment your father said “door”. So, you live this. For you to live this, you have to be observing

yourself: a secondary self-observing the primary self-living that situation. And children with autism have a problem with this secondary self, because this secondary self the child acquires in contact with the mother, with the mirror neuron system as mediator. But since the mirror neuron system of the child with autism is impaired, contact with the mother is impaired. He does not acquire this secondary self well, he does not talk to himself, and he does not have this supervisor self on top of himself. So, he cannot talk to himself and see his own experiences – because that’s how we talk to others. When we are going to speak, for example, to explain to a person what a cow is, we refer to an experience we had. We describe what we felt when we encountered a cow: “ah, I met it, it’s a big animal, it has horns, etc.” Then I will conceptualize the cow. But the autistic person does not have this context. He does not live this context, because he does not have reciprocity, because he does not have an adequate mirror neuron system. So, he does not have this context with another person.

And then, for example, we have several polysemic situations, that is, in which a concept has several meanings – it depends on the context. So, for example, “that woman is a broody hen” means a nervous woman, a woman who protects her children, who is very nervous. “That guy is a horse” means an aggressive guy. “Ah, my brother-in-law is a dog” means my brother-in-law does not have a good character. “Ah, that woman is a cow,” that is, that woman is disrespectful, inelegant, brutish. So, these words have little to do with the animal. For example, the dog itself is loyal. But it is the context that produces this. So, it is not the lexicon – and the autistic person is fixated on the lexicon – and it is the context that produces this. And this context, the autistic person does not live with the other. So, he often learns words by imposition or by convention. So, it was conventionally established that this is a ball.

It would be expected that, given these great conceptual difficulties, all children with autism would have severe intellectual deficiencies. But why are many intelligent? It is the same as artificial intelligence is intelligent. That ball – you can conventionally establish that that ball can unfortunately pejoratively represent an obese individual. So, you say: “the ball can mean that you are like a ball,” “that person is as fat as a ball”. The ball can mean a sphere: planet Earth is a ball. The ball can mean something that rolls, for example: “that wheel was rolling like a ball,” “it was not walking, it was rolling like a ball”. So, this “ball,” you can give to a person with autism, or to a computer – artificial intelligence, several meanings that should be experienced emotionally, in a synchronic context with other people. But some children with autism do not experience this. The therapist can conceptualize this experience – this emotional and synchronic experience with other people. So, for example, to conventionally establish that “ball” can also mean a planet, for example. Ball can mean a fuller person. So, in this case, the force of logic makes them intelligent, just as it can happen with artificial intelligence. But they did not experience that concept within a synchronic context with other people. If the child with autism has the brain capacity to assimilate all those meanings, he does not need contexts and emotionality’s to understand the meaning – since the multiplicity of concepts provided can supply these contexts (“ball can be a plastic object,” “ball can be a planet,” “ball can be a sphere to play on the ground (marble),” etc.). So, that’s why many who do not have this intelligence – many people with autism spectrum disorder who do not have this superlative intelligence to assimilate so many concepts, then they also start to have a reduced repertoire. And then, their language will be limited. It will be limited only to that simple and unique ball.

Methods

This article is based on the longitudinal clinical observation of children with ASD attended at the Asmigo Child Psychiatric Hospital, in Goiânia (GO), Brazil, over 45 years. Also incorporated are: practical experiences in medico-pedagogical centers for autism since 1986; theoretical training and supervised internships in French child psychiatry and neurological rehabilitation institutions; and a review of neuropsychological, psychodynamic, and neurofunctional literature applied to ASD. The methodology is essentially qualitative, centered on clinical reflections and theoretical foundations.

Results

Observations indicate that most autistic individuals learn language through direct association between word and object (imposition), without reference to affective or social contexts. This process differs from the symbolic acquisition of language, which is based on shared experiences and the reflexive function of the secondary self. Deficiency in the mirror neuron system appears to compromise this process, reducing the capacity for narrative elaboration, polysemic contextualization, and metaphorical use.

Language as Experience, Not as Imposition

The neurotypical child learns words within lived and shared contexts. When the father says: “close the door and come here to daddy,” the word “door” is associated with an emotional and interactive situation, and not just an object. This type of learning depends on empathy, mirror neurons, and the internalization of experiences. The autistic individual, on the other hand, tends to learn by “imposition”: words are like plaques directly associated with objects, without reference to

shared experiences. This form of learning is favored by behaviorist methods, such as ABA, which strengthen direct lexical associations, often at the expense of emotional experience.

The Mirror Neuron and the Secondary Self

Symbolic development requires more than an association between word and object – it requires the child to see himself living the situation. For this, a secondary self that observes the primary self in action is necessary. This reflective self is acquired in initial contact with the mother and with significant figures, mediated by a functional mirror neuron system. Children with autism frequently present deficits in these systems. Without this reflective capacity, they do not “talk to themselves” – and, therefore, do not construct concepts from shared affective experiences. Autism, thus, is less a “cognitive failure” and more a failure in the constitution of the symbolic subject.

The Problem of Polysemy and Limited Repertoire

Everyday language is full of polysemic expressions. When someone is called “a cow,” “a horse,” or “a dog,” the reference is metaphorical and culturally constructed. The autistic individual, with their literal learning, loses this layer of meaning. The lexicon is fixed, but the context is lost.

Words like “ball” can mean the toy, the planet, an obese person, a rolling movement, among others. For those who have learned only by imposition, this semantic richness vanishes. And if the autistic individual does not possess a high formal intelligence that allows them to absorb such associations by pure logic, their communicative repertoire becomes even more restricted.

The Autistic Brain and Artificial Intelligence: A Partial Analogy

Many autistic individuals are considered “intelligent” because they can attribute multiple meanings to the same term, like artificial intelligence. However, this does not imply experience or empathy. It is a formal, not emotional, logic. They may understand that “ball” can mean “planet,” but they have not experienced this concept emotionally and shared it with others. This dissociation between meaning and experience is one of the most central and most neglected traits of autism.

Therapeutic Dimension: Between Imposition and Relational Experience

The therapeutic choice in autism needs to consider the degree of empathetic functionality of the child. Imposition methods, such as ABA, are useful in severe cases, when there is no possibility of affective reciprocity. However, many children with ASD possess some degree of emotional synchrony, capacity for imitation, and sharing – potentialities that should be stimulated, not inhibited. Mechanical and repetitive therapies, when applied indiscriminately, stifle the development of the symbolic self. This is where the contribution of the Bretonneau School in Tours (France) comes in, with its Therapies of Exchange and Development, formulated by child psychiatrists such as Philippe Lelord and Bernard Sauvage. In this approach, the focus is not on reinforcing responses, but on the progressive construction of bonding, gaze, affectivity, and inner language. These therapies are based on the principle that language emerges from affect and relationship, not from imposition. Children who still possess some capacity for imitation and emotional interaction should be led to sharing experiences, not to the mechanization of response. The objective is to favor the constitution of the observing self, capable of narrating to itself, living its concepts, and symbolizing its experiences.

Discussion

The absence of an “observing self” leads to difficulty in recognizing the intentions, affects, and symbolizations of the other. Without this reference, language is reduced to code and loses expressive function. Methods like ABA, by reinforcing imposition, can inhibit symbolic emergence in children with some degree of affective reciprocity. On the other hand, therapies such as Therapies exchange et de Développement (TED), developed by Lelord, Barthélémy, and Sauvage at the Bretonneau School, promote the construction of bonding, gaze, and body-affective synchrony, as prerequisites for the emergence of subjective language [1–3]. These therapies are based on stimulating the empathetic system and the progressive formation of the secondary self [4,5].

The Therapeutic Dimension: Between Imposition and Relational Experience

What is at stake is not only the autistic person’s linguistic comprehension, but also how it is therapeutically addressed. As previously pointed out, behavioral methods, such as ABA, are based on lexical imposition: directly associating words with objects or actions in a repetitive and decontextualized manner. Although this can bring some functional gain in severe cases, this type of approach neglects the deepest aspect of human language – its experiential, relational, and symbolic nature. Most children with autism are not incapable of all forms of exchange.

Many still possess some degree of functionality in mirror neuron systems, some capacity for affective synchrony and emotional sharing. These elements are essential for the child to develop the so-called secondary self – the ability to observe

himself in his experiences, and, with that, elaborate concepts, meanings, and internal narratives. Unfortunately, even these children who present relational potential are frequently subjected to purely structured, mechanical therapies, centered only on reinforcing expected responses. These interventions can inhibit the development of the symbolic subject and inner language.

In this context, the work developed by the Bretonneau School, in Tours (France), which proposes a psychodynamic and relational approach to autism, stands out. Psychiatrists like Philippe Lelord and Bernard Sauvage developed the model of Therapies of Exchange and Development, which emphasizes working on gaze, gesture, affective reciprocity, and the construction of the bond with the therapist. This school, influenced by authors such as Henri Wallon and René Spitz, proposes that language can only truly emerge when there is emotional sharing and synchronization with the other. Therefore, the choice of therapeutic strategy should not be generalized, but adapted to the child's relational capacity. Severely compromised children, who cannot establish any form of synchrony, may benefit from structured methods. But those with some openness to the other should be treated in a way that strengthens their possibilities of symbolic construction, subjectivity, and reflective language – and not annulled by methods of pure repetition.

Critical Approach to the Findings

These findings and reflections can have originality and clinical value, especially for some reasons that we detail below:

Unique integration of diverse areas

It articulates:

- Clinical linguistics
- Neuropsychology (mirror neuron, secondary self)
- Affective experience in language acquisition
- Symbolic concepts (metaphor, polysemy, popular saying)
- Epistemological critique of behavioral therapies (ABA)
- Clinical attention to residual relational potential in autistic individuals

This intertwining of symbolic experience and therapeutic syntax does not always appear clearly in the literature – not even in authors such as Jean-Claude Maleval, Bernard Golse, or Tony Attwood. Most either stick to behaviorism or fragmented psychodynamic approaches. We show how the failure of metaphorical language in autism points to deep constitutive failures, and translate this into practical clinical decisions.

Well-Articulated Critique of the Indiscriminate Use of Certain Therapeutic Methods Very Focused on a Behaviorist Imposition

We do not make an ideological critique of behaviorism, as some psychoanalysts do, but a clinical and functional one, by showing that:

- Loovas can be useful for very severe cases;
- But that it is being used as a standard for children who still have the capacity for exchange;
- And this prevents the blossoming of the symbolic self and shared language.

Rescue of the Concept of “Secondary Self” with Empirical Basis

The idea that the autistic person has a failure in the constitution of the reflective self (or secondary self) appears punctually in French authors (Ey, Wallon, Bergès), but it is almost never used on a practical basis or associated with the mirror neuron system, as we do here. The way you show that without this secondary self-there is no internal narrative or understanding of metaphors, has a certain originality.

Clinical Application of Tours therapies

The citation of the Bretonneau School (Lelord, Sauvage, Barthelemy) is little known even among specialists. Bringing this into contemporary discussion, and placing it as a more experiential alternative to mechanical therapies, renews the therapeutic debate based on practice and not just on ideology.

The Originality of Common Language as a Clinical Marker

The use of popular sayings and metaphorical expressions as a diagnostic and therapeutic key is practically unprecedented. Few works focus on this. Our argument is that the inability to understand these expressions shows the degree of symbolic loss and the function of the other in the formation of the subject. This is clinical, practical, and original.

Therefore, we could say that these findings present a theoretical, clinical, and therapeutic contribution. They dialogue with classic authors, but advance in the sense of integrating experience, language, symbolism, and intervention. This expansion

inserts a critical therapeutic dimension and allows for reinforcing the argument against the indiscriminate use of behavioral “imposition” methods for all children with ASD, even those with potential for relational development. The reference to the Bretonneau School, to Dr. Bernard Golse, Michel Lemay, Lelord, Philippe Sauvage, and their relational and developmental approaches opens space for a substantiated critique of the current behaviorist hegemony.

Conclusion

Metaphorical language requires a shared experience of the world. In autism, the failure in this experience leads to a limitation in symbolic understanding, which should be approached clinically with strategies appropriate to the child’s level of reciprocity. The indiscriminate use of mechanical methods, even in cases with relational potential, can compromise subjective constitution and symbolic autonomy. Therefore, the valorization of developmental and relational therapies is advocated, which promote human flourishing in language and affect. The difficulty of autistic individuals in understanding sayings and metaphors is not superficial. It points to a deeper failure: the absence of symbolic experience mediated by empathy and affective exchange. Human language, by its very nature, requires context, emotion, and otherness. The clinical practice of autism must, therefore, set aside rigid and generalizing models and open itself to approaches that promote the rooting of language in the body, in effect, and in lived experience with the other.

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